

respectively. Weed population was recorded at harvest on four 1-m² quadrats. Yield was recorded from the whole plot.

As propanil dose increased, weed density declined. Rice yield doubled at the lowest herbicide dose and more than tripled at higher doses. In untreated plots, yield loss was 74% (Table 1).

Table 2 shows the effect of weeds on yield components. Yield reduction was highly related to the decrease in panicles/unit area. In heavily infested plots (treatments 1 and 2), rice density was reduced by 1/3 to 1/2 as compared to density with good control (treatment 6), indicating that yield loss was due not only to competition between weeds and rice for soil nutrients and light but also to death of rice seedlings at early growth stages. At about 70 DS, weeds became taller than rice plants, reducing photosynthesis at preflowering and grain formation. Spikelets/panicle and percentage empty spikelets were significantly reduced in untreated and low-dose plots. Weight of 1,000 grains was not affected by weed

Table 1. Herbicide application and economic return for irrigated, broadcast rice, Solomon Islands.^a

Treatment	Dosage (kg ai/ha) of propanil	Weeds/m ² (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield loss (%)	Gain ^b (US\$/ha)
1	0	505 d	1.1 d	74	—
2	0.76	207 c	2.1 c	52	210
3	1.08	64 b	3.6 b	18	550
4	1.44	22 ab	4.2 ab	6	670
5	1.80	10 ab	3.9 ab	11	615
6	2.16	1 a	4.4 a	—	723

^aSeparation of means by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level. ^bGain was estimated by comparing with yield of the untreated plots, using current prices on paddy (\$225/t) and propanil (Stam F34 e.c.) (\$2.90/litre).

Table 2. Yield and yield components of broadcast rice at different weed densities,^a Solomon Islands.

Treatment	Panicles/m ²	Grains/panicle (no.)	% empty grain	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)
1	160 c	50 b	22 a	29 a	1.1 d
2	207 bc	55 b	27 b	30 a	2.1 c
3	293 ab	60 ab	25 ab	30 a	3.6 b
4	331 ab	77 a	23 a	30 a	4.2 ab
5	273 b	74 a	24 ab	28 a	3.9 b
6	376 a	71 a	24 ab	29 a	4.4 a

^a Means of four 50-m² plots served as 4 replications. Yield components were obtained from 5 plants in each replication, Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

infestation. Broadleaf weeds did not affect crop growth because seedling

establishment was good and homogeneous. □

Efficiency of herbicide carriers for lowland rice weed control

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We studied the efficiency of herbicide carriers for weed control in the All India Coordinated Research Programme on Weed Control in 1984 wet season at TNAU. An emulsifiable concentrate (EC) formulation of thiobencarb at 1.5 kg/ha was mixed with easily available carriers: farmyard manure (2, 4, or 6 kg/ha), rice bran and husk (2, 4, or 6 kg/ha), soil (12.5, 25, or 50 kg/ha), sand (50 kg/ha), or water (750 litres/ha) and applied 5 d after transplanting (DT) with 3 to 5 cm standing water in the field. The mixtures were compared with a control pre-emergence sprinkle application of oxadiazon EC (0.48 or 0.72 kg/ha) and an unweeded control,

In the control plots, weed density/m² at 30 and 50 DT was 50 and 196 for *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) Beauv., 22

Efficiency of herbicide carriers for weed control on rice, Coimbatore, India.

Carrier and quantity per ha		Treatment	Weed wt ^a (g/m ²)		Productive tillers (no./5 plants)	Grain yield (t/ha)
		Preemergence herbicide and dose (kg/ha)	30 DT	50 DT		
Farmyard manure		Thiobencarb				
	2 kg	1.5	48	124	57	5.2
	4 kg	1.5	46	112	63	5.6
Rice bran and husk	6 kg	1.5	22	153	61	5.5
	2 kg	1.5	31	93	53	5.3
	4 kg	1.5	15	123	58	5.8
Soil	6 kg	1.5	41	119	59	5.7
	12.5 kg	1.5	43	147	57	5.3
	25 kg	1.5	66	108	57	5.8
Sand, 50 kg	50 kg	1.5	24	84	60	5.0
	Water, 500 litres	1.5	34	132	54	5.8
	EC formulation	1.5	26	166	59	5.4
direct spraying		Oxadiazon				
	4 litres	0.48	36	178	58	4.7
	6 litres	0.72	28	120	64	5.9
No herbicide or weeding	—		84	300	49	3.2
CD			6	8	1	0.5

^a DT = days after transplanting.

and 32 for *Paspalum* sp., 18 and 126 for *Cyperus difformis* (L.), 6 and 18 for *Marsilea quadrifolia* L., and 28 and 8 for *Monochoria vaginalis* L. Thiobencarb

with different carriers at all rates effectively controlled annual grasses and sedges, but not *Paspalum* sp.

Treatments reduced weed dry matter

and increased productive tillers and IR50 grain yield (see table). There was little difference between carriers. Preemergence oxadiazon EC reduced early rice growth

but effectively controlled grasses, sedges, and aquatic weeds such as *Marsilea quadrifolia* and *Monochoria vaginalis*. It gave 4.7-5.9 t grain yield/ha compared with

3.7 t/ha for the unweeded plot. Mixing an EC formulation of preemergence herbicide with carriers, or direct sprinkling, is simple and economical. □

Rice field weeds of Mwea Irrigation Scheme, Kenya

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The Mwea Irrigation Scheme is the largest rice growing area in Kenya. It is near Mount Kenya, about 100 km north

Weeds of Mwea Irrigation Scheme, Kenya.^a

Weed species	Lifeform	Habitat
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) DC.	E	XO ●
<i>Ammannia auriculata</i> Willd.	E	XO
<i>A. baccifera</i> L.	E	X ●
<i>A. prieuriana</i> Guill & Perr.	E	XO ●
<i>Aponogeton absynicum</i> Hochst. ex A. Rich	FL	X ●
<i>Ceratophyllum demersum</i> L.	S	X ■ θ●
<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	E	XO ▲ θ●
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	E	XO θ●
<i>C. immensus</i> C. B. Clarke	E	XO θ●
<i>C. latifolius</i> Poir	E	XO θ●
<i>Diplachne caudata</i> K. Schum	E	XO θ●
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	E	XO θ●
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> Sw.	E	XO ▲ θ●
<i>Lemna minor</i> L.	FF	X ●
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i> (Jacq.) Raven	E	XO ●
<i>L. prostrata</i> Roxb.	E	XO ●
<i>L. stolonifera</i> (Guill. & Perr.) Raven	E	XO ▲ θ●
<i>Mariscus assimilis</i> (Steud.) Podlech	E	XO θ●
<i>Marsilea macrocarpa</i> Presl.	FL	XO ▲ θ●
<i>Najas graminea</i> Del.	S	XI ■ θ●
<i>Nymphaea caerulea</i> Savign	FL	X θ●
<i>Ricciocarpus natans</i> (L.) Corda	FF	X
<i>Scirpus confusus</i> N. E. Brown	E	XO θ●
<i>Sesbania sesban</i> (L.) Merr	E	XO θ●
<i>Sphaeranthus bullatus</i> Mattf.	E	XO ●
<i>S. cyathuloides</i> O. Hoffm.	E	XO ●
<i>S. suaveolens</i> (Forsk.) DC.	E	XO ▲ θ●
<i>Typha angustifolia</i> L.	E	XO ■ θ●
<i>T. latifolia</i> L.	E	XO ■ θ●

^aE = emergent, FL = floating-leaved, S = submersed, FF = free-floating, X = inside rice crop, O = on levees of major canals, ■ = inside major canals, ▲ = inside major canals but floating, θ = inside feeder canal, ● = inside drains.

Frequency (%)

Distribution of weeds at Mwea Irrigation Scheme, Kenya, 1980-81 growing season.

of Nairobi. We identified the rice field weeds and examined their distribution.

Twenty-nine weeds were identified (see table). According to Sculthorpe's life-form categories, 22 were emergent, 3 floating-leaved, 2 submersed, and 2 free-floating. The major habitats of the weeds were within the rice crop, on the levees of major canals, and inside feeder canals and drains.

Weed distribution was studied in 1980-81 and percentage frequency was scored in 1000 1-m² quadrats. The figure shows the distribution has bimodal peaks

in Sep and Mar. The general decline in weed population between Sep and Dec might be attributed to weeding at the initial stages and drainage as the rice crop matures. The increase between Jan and Mar is due to reflooding and the subsequent reemergence of obligately aquatic weeds. Puddling and rototilling reduce weeds in Aug, when fields are prepared for the next season. The weeds could not be totally eradicated in Dec when dry-land conditions were prevalent because of the persistence of some weeds and nonuniform field preparation. □

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Reaction of some upland rices to root-knot nematodes in rubber plantation fields

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In 1984, upland rice lines that were

grown and selected for intercropping in a pararubber crop at Kok-Primeng Rubber Experiment Station were seriously damaged by the root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne* spp. Infested plants had root galling, yellowed leaves and leaf sheaths, stunting, and low tillering. Based on the number of root galls, some lines had resistance to the nematode (see table). □